

Assessment of Selected Yoghurts in Birnin Kebbi Metropolis, Kebbi State: A Study on Safety and Quality Parameters

¹Yusuf, A. B. and ²Shehu, A.

¹Department of Biochemistry and Molecular Biology, Federal University Birnin Kebbi, Kebbi State, Nigeria

²Association for Promotion of Food Safety and Improved Nutrition Kebbi State Chapter

*Correspondence: Yusuf Abdulrahman Bashir; Federal University Birnin Kebbi, Department of Biochemistry and Molecular Biology; PMB 1157, Birnin Kebbi, Kebbi State, Nigeria; yusuf.abdulrahman@fubk.edu.ng; <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3800-443X>

Submission: 26th May, 2024; Accepted: 26th June, 2024; Published: 30th June, 2024

Abstract

Yoghurt is the main fermented and well-patronized dairy product produced commercially within Birnin Kebbi Metropolis of Kebbi State, Nigeria. As far as the nutritional composition is concerned, some of the produced yoghurts are either not labelled or inadequately labelled. The aim of this research was to evaluate the safety and quality of selected yoghurts sold in Birnin Kebbi Metropolis, Kebbi State. A total of four commercialized brands of yoghurts were collected within Birnin Kebbi Metropolis. The brands were coded as A1, A2, A3 and A4 and they were analyzed for proximate composition, peroxide value and free fatty acid and the presence of coliform. Statistical analysis was done using one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA). The results revealed there were significant differences ($p < 0.05$) in moisture, ash, fat, protein, and carbohydrate contents of all the 4 brands of yoghurt. The moisture content of all the four samples ranged from 77.00 to 89.30%, ash ranged from 0.5 to 1.5%, fat ranged from 2.80 to 4.20%, protein ranged from 1.85 to 2.75% and carbohydrate ranging from 4.90 to 15.35%. There was also significant difference ($p < 0.05$) in the peroxide values of all the four samples. A1 had the lowest peroxide value of 7.75meq/ml, while A2 had the highest peroxide value of 10.50meq/ml. The percentage free fatty acids obtained in the samples ranged from 0.42 to 0.78. The result indicates zero coliforms in all the samples. These variations could be attributed to the differences in the compositions of the raw materials used and the methods of production. The findings of this study reveal that all the four brands of yoghurt are of good quality with regards to the parameters evaluated. Although some parameters of proximate analysis did not align with established standards, the complete absence of coliforms indicates a high level of adherence to strict manufacturing practices and a commitment to quality control. Therefore, this study suggests the need for continual quality assessment and adherence to regulatory standards to ensure consistent product quality and safety in yogurts sold in Nigeria.

Keywords: Birnin Kebbi, Nutritional Composition, Safety, Quality, and Yoghurt

1.0 Introduction

Yogurt also spelled yoghurt or yoghourt is considered by most regulatory agencies worldwide to be a fermented milk product that provides digested lactose and specifically defined, viable bacterial strains typically *Streptococcus thermophilus* and *Lactobacillus bulgaricus* [1]. The word “Yoghurt” comes from the Turkish word “Yogurtmak”, meaning to

thicken, coagulate or curdle [2]. Yoghurt is frequently taken as a drink or prepared together with *Fura* in the northern part of Nigeria due to the quality of nutrients present [1]. Yoghurt is the main fermented and well-patronized dairy product produced commercially within the Birnin Kebbi Metropolis of Kebbi State, Nigeria.

Yoghurt is an ancient food that has gone by many names over the millennia. It is also believed that

yoghurt was originated in Mesopotamia now in Iraq thousands of years ago [2]. It is believed that milk products were incorporated into the human diet around 10000-5000BC, with the domestication of milk producing animals (cows, sheep, and goats as well as horses, buffalo and camels) [2].

However, milk spoiled easily, making it difficult to use at that time. Herdsmen in the Middle East carried milk in bags made of intestinal gut, it was discovered that contact with intestinal juices caused the milk to curdle and sour, preserving it and allowing for conservation of a dairy product for extended periods of time [3]. The partial digestion of the milk caused by the fermentation of the starter culture makes yoghurt easily digested, even by people who cannot tolerate milk. It is a rich source of protein and calcium, and the fermentation process makes these nutrients easier to absorb [3].

Probiotics provide antioxidative properties and stimulate the immune system, which are strain-dependent effects that have been the subject of many recent studies [4]. To capitalize on the potential health benefits of probiotics, they must be delivered at high doses through foods such as yoghurt [5]. The foremost challenge is maintaining appropriate probiotic numbers during processing and storage, as insufficient doses at the time of consumption will not provide the intended health benefits [6]. The number of probiotic bacteria needed to provide health benefits is unclear however, to achieve the desired therapeutic effects, probiotics should be consumed regularly, and the product should contain at least 10⁶–10⁸cfu/ml during shelf life [7].

Enough probiotic should reach and colonize the intestines *in vivo* [8]; [9]; [10]. Probiotic foods are supplemented with other active components to provide additional functional properties. Fresh and dried fruit mixes improve yoghurt's nutritional value and taste, and fruit enhancement plays a considerable role in yoghurt consumption and sales [8] and [10].

These probiotics are defined as Live Microorganisms which when administered in adequate amounts confer a health benefit on the host [11], one of the most accepted approaches through which the gut microbiota composition can be influenced through the use of probiotics,

which are life microbial dietary additive. Besides the nutritional values, ingestion of lactic acid bacteria (LAB) and their fermented food has been suggested to confer a range of health benefits including immune system modulation, increased resistances to malignancy and infection illness [8].

Fermented products have been an acceptable and essential part of diets in most parts of the world for several centuries. Yoghurt is one of the oldest fermented milk products known. Fermentation of milk involves the action of microorganisms, principally the lactic acid bacteria. These microorganisms sour the milk by converting the milk sugar lactose to lactic acid [12].

In the food industry in general and in the dairy industry specifically, microorganisms are of great importance. One specific group of relevance is the lactic acid bacteria. LAB are characterized by their capacity to ferment lactose to lactic acid and they are naturally present in raw milk [2]. Yoghurt is said to be low in saturated fatty acids and cholesterol level, but is nutritionally rich in protein and vitamins such as, calcium, iron, potassium, and phosphorus, which maintain the red blood cells, improve the good function of the nervous system in human body [13]. Yoghurt is said to prevent high blood pressure in hypertensive people. The proteins, carbohydrate and vitamins contents present in Yoghurt are found to be greater compared to those in fresh milk. However, there is little difference between fresh milk and Yoghurt product in terms of energy and sugar contents. This is to say that the sweeter Yoghurt provides more energy when compared to fresh milk [1].

[1] posited that there are two types of commercially prepared Yoghurts produced in Birnin Kebbi metropolis. These are: the powdered Yoghurt and the soft or liquid yoghurt. But the most commonly produced type in Birnin Kebbi metropolis is the soft Yoghurt [1]. However, in Northern Nigeria Yoghurt is a very important product of “*Fura*” delicacy which gives Yoghurt its paramount importance as many people now prefer Yoghurt with *Fura* than as it was originally known to be taken with fresh cow milk. Therefore, the current study evaluated the safety and quality of selected commercial yoghurts sold in Birnin Kebbi metropolis.

2.0 Materials and Methods

2.1 Study area

The study was conducted in Birnin Kebbi metropolis of Kebbi State, located in the North-western part of Nigeria. Kebbi state lies between latitude 10°N to 13°N and longitude 4°E to 6°E. The state enjoys a tropical climate, characterized by two extreme seasons: hot and cold. Rainfall occurs from May/June to October, with the heaviest falls in July and August. The cold harmattan period, often accompanied by dusty winds and fog, prevails from November to January. Mean annual temperatures range from 21°C to 38°C, while mean annual rainfall is approximately 500mm [14].

Kebbi is one of the states bordering the Sahelian nation of Niger and Benin Republics on the western part, Sokoto State on the northeast and Niger State on the south [15]. It has an estimated population of 3.8 million, total land area of 36,800 km², and administratively divided into 21 Local Government Areas. The main ethnic groups are Arawa, Hausa, and Fulani with a significant population of settlers tribes like Yoruba, Nupe, and Igbo. The main occupations of the inhabitants are farming, trading, and fishing. Islam and Christianity are the predominant religion with some practicing traditional religion [15].

2.2 Sample Collection for the purpose of this study

Yoghurt samples were collected from four (4) different Yoghurt brands in Birnin Kebbi. The four (4) yoghurt brands selected for the sample collection were Gamji, Rufaida, De-nice, and Azan. The samples were designated as A1, A2, A3 and A4, respectively.

2.3 Methods

2.4 Determination of Proximate Composition of the Yoghurt samples

This study adopted standard analytical procedures for food analysis to determine moisture content, crude protein, crude fibre, percentage lipids, carbohydrate, ash and caloric value as recommended by the Association of Official Analytical Chemists [16].

2.4.1 Moisture content

From the ground sample, 2g was put into a crucible, dried in an oven (Leniscope, England) at 105°C overnight. The dried sample was cooled in a dessicator for 30 minutes and weighed. The percentage moisture content of the samples was then calculated using the formula:

$$\% \text{Moisture} = \frac{\text{Weight difference} \times 100}{\text{Original weight of the sample}}$$

Where weight difference = original weight of sample – final weight of sample [16].

2.4.2 Ash content

From the ground sample, 2g was placed in crucible and ashed in a muffle furnace (Lenton furnaces, England) at 600°C for 3 hours. The hot crucible was then cooled in a dessicator and weighed. The percentage residue weighed was expressed as ash content [16]. The percentage weight of the ash was then calculated as shown below:

$$\% \text{ASH} = \frac{(\text{Weight of the sample+crucible}) - \text{weight of crucible}}{\text{Original weight of sample}}$$

2.4.3 Crude lipid content

From the ground sample, 2g was used for determining crude lipid by extracting lipid from it for 5 hours with petroleum ether in a Soxhlet extractor [16]. The percentage fat content of the samples was then calculated using the formula:

$$\% \text{ fat} = \frac{(\text{weight of extract+cup}) - \text{weight of cup} \times 100}{\text{Original weight of sample}}$$

2.4.4 Crude fibre content

From the ground sample, 2g was used to estimate crude fibre by acid and alkaline digestion methods with 20% H₂SO₄ and NaOH solution [16]. From the ground sample, 2g was weighed into the fibre flask and 100ml of 0.255N H₂SO₄ was added. The mixture was then heat under reflux for 1 hour with the heating mantle. The hot mixture was filter through a sieve cloth. The filtrate obtained was then discard and the residue was return to the fibre flask to which 100ml of (0.313N NaOH) was added and heated under reflux for another 1 hour. Then the mixture was filter through the fibre sieve cloth and 10ml of

acetone was added to dissolve any organic constituents. The residue was washed with about 50ml of hot water on the sieve cloth before it was finally transfer into the crucible. Then the residue inside the crucible was oven dried at 105°C overnight to drive off the moisture. The oven-dried crucible containing the residue was cool in a desiccator and weigh as designated as W_1 . The crucible with weight W_1 was then transferred to the muffle furnace for Ashing at 550°C for 4 hours. Then the crucible containing white or grey ash (free carbonaceous materials) was allowed to cool in a desiccator and was weighed to obtain W_2 . The percentage of fibre was obtained by using the formula below:

$$\% \text{ Crude fibre} = \frac{W_1 - W_2 \times 100}{\text{Wt.of sample} \times 1}$$

2.4.5 Protein determination

Crude protein was determined by Lowry method as described by [17]. Exactly 5ml of each of the samples was weighed and dissolved in 5ml of phosphate buffer. The mixture was then separated and the supernatant was used for the analysis. Exactly 0.2ml of each of the sample solution was taken into a separate test tube and 5 ml reagent C was added. The solution was made up to 10ml with distil water and was allow to stand for 10 minutes at room temperature. 0.4ml of reagent D was added to all the test tubes. The solutions were then mixed and incubated in dark for 30 minutes. The absorbance of the solutions was taken at 660nm using spectrophotometer. The absorbance value was compared with standard value and protein concentration was calculated from the standard curve (graph).

$$\% \text{ Conc. of protein} = \frac{\mu\text{g of protein} \times \text{Dilution factor} (10)}{\text{volume of sample}} \times 0.001$$

$\mu\text{g of protein}$ = concentration of protein from the graph

2.4.6 Carbohydrate determination

The carbohydrate content was determined using this formula:

$$\text{Available Carbohydrate (\%)} = [100 - \% \text{ Protein} + \% \text{Moisture} + \% \text{ Ash} + \% \text{ Fibre} + \% \text{ Crude Lipid}]$$

2.5 Peroxide Value Determination

The peroxide value was determined using the method described by [16]. Exactly 2ml of the yoghurt sample was weighed into a clean dry flask and 22 cm³ of the mixture of 10 cm³ of acetic acid and 12 cm³ of chloroform was added, then 0.5 cm³ of potassium iodide were also added. The flask was closed and allowed to stay with constant shaking for 1 minute. 30 cm³ of distilled water was then added and titrated against 0.1 M of sodium thiosulphate (Na₂S₂O₃) solution until an initial yellow colour disappeared and a faint blue colour appeared. The titration continued after the addition of 0.5 cm³ of starch indicator until there was a sudden disappearance of the blue colour, which signifies the end point. The peroxide value is often reported as the mL of 20 mM Na₂S₂O₃ per gram of sample. Thus, peroxide value was calculated using the equation below.

$$\text{Peroxide value} = \frac{(S-B) \times M \times 100}{W}$$

where: peroxide value= m Eq of peroxide per 100 g of sample, S-sample titre value (cm³). B-blank titre value (cm³), M= molarity of Na₂S₂O₃ (mEq/cm³), W=weight of flour

2.6 Free Fatty Acids

Free fatty acids were determined according to the method described by [16]. Exactly 2ml of the yoghurt sample was transferred into a 250 cm³ Erlenmeyer flask followed by the addition of 100 cm³ of ethanol and 2 cm³ of phenolphthalein indicator. After mixing the content properly, it was titrated against 0.04 M NaOH. The shaking continued until a slight pink colour was observed, which was steady for about 30 seconds and signified the end point. The % of free fatty acids was calculated using the below equation.

$$\% \text{FFA} = \frac{V \times M \times 28.2}{W}$$

where: % FFA = percentage of free fatty acids, V= average volume of NaOH used (cm³), M = molarity of NaOH, W = weight of the flour sample

2.7 Coliform Detection Test

The coliform detection was carried out by standard multiple tube fermentation technique. Presumptive Test: The presumptive test was carried out using lactose broth medium containing malt extract (3.0 g/L), peptone (10 g/L), lactose (5.0 g/L) and Bromothymol blue indicator (1.0 g/L). Exactly 10 ml of lactose broth medium was transferred into the test tubes. After that, drown tubes were dropped into the test tubes and exactly 5ml of the yoghurt samples were added. After 24 h incubation at 37°C the test tubes were examined for the presence of acid and gas. Acid production is indicated by a change in

3.0 Results

Table 1: Percentage proximate composition of the yoghurt samples

Parameters	Sample A1	Sample A2	Sample A3	Sample A4
Moisture	77.0 ^a ±0.35	89.3 ^b ±0.35	83.5 ^c ±0.35	80.3 ^d ±0.35
Ash	1.5 ^a ±0.0	0.5 ^b ±0.35	1.0 ^{ab} ±0.00	0.5 ^b ±0.35
Crude fat	4.20 ^a ±0.07	2.80 ^b ±0.07	3.02 ^c ±0.01	3.20 ^c ±0.08
Protein	1.95 ^a ±0.03	2.75 ^c ±0.07	2.25 ^b ±0.03	1.85 ^a ±0.03
Fiber	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Carbohydrate	15.35 ^a ±0.07	4.90 ^b ±0.07	10.23 ^c ±0.16	9.43 ^d ±0.07

Values are mean ± standard deviation of duplicate determinations, values bearing same superscript in a row are not significantly ($P>0.05$) different.

Table 2: Peroxide value of the yoghurt samples

Samples	Peroxide value (meq/ml)
A1	7.75 ^a ±0.01
A2	10.50 ^b ±0.21
A3	9.00 ^c ±0.14
A4	8.50 ^d ±0.14

Values are mean± standard deviation of duplicate determinations, values bearing same superscript in a column are not significantly ($P>0.05$) different.

Table 3: Percentage free fatty acid of the yoghurt samples

Samples	% Free fatty acid
A1	0.45 ^a ±0.01
A2	0.78 ^b ±0.01
A3	0.42 ^a ±0.00
A4	0.51 ^c ±0.00

Values are mean± standard deviation of duplicate determinations, values bearing same superscript in a column are not significantly ($P>0.05$) different.

colour and while gas production is indicated by the accumulation of gas bubbles in the inverted Durham tubes (Feng *et al.*, 2002).

2.8 Statistical analysis

Results were presented as mean values and standard deviations. Data were subjected to one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) and difference were considered to be significant at ($p < 0.05$). Using Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 20.

Table 4: Microbial count (coliform) of the yoghurt samples

Samples	Coliform (cfu/ml)
A1	0.0
A2	0.0
A3	0.0
A4	0.0

No coliform was detected in all sample evaluated

4.0 Discussion

The results of the proximate compositions of the four yoghurt samples as presented in Table 1 revealed that there were significant differences ($p < 0.05$) in moisture, ash, fat, protein, and carbohydrate contents of all the 4 brands of yoghurt. For moisture content samples A2 and A1 recorded the highest and lowest values respectively. However, samples A1, A3 and A4 recorded moisture content within recommended standard reference range reported by [19] which posited that the maximum moisture content of

yoghurt should be 84%, as much water in yoghurt makes it less viscous thereby affecting texture and mouth feel. The ash contents were low in all the samples, with A1 having the highest value. The level of ash in the samples is of nutritional significance as it is an indication of the mineral content which required for various biochemical processes [20].

The fat contents of A2, A3, and A4 were within the range reported for similar products by [21] and [22] with the fat content of A1 higher than the reported range. There was a significant difference ($p < 0.05$) in the crude fat content of A1 compared to A2, whereas, there was no significant difference ($p > 0.05$) between A3 and A4. It has been reported that the percentage of fat content plays a vital role in yoghurts since it improves the texture, appearance, flavour, and taste of yoghurts [23]. According to the Codex Standards for yoghurts [24], yoghurt should have less than 15% of fat content. The results from our studies showed that the fat content of the above four samples complied with these standards.

The result of the protein content is within the range previously reported by [25]. The lowest protein content was recorded in A4, this was found to be significantly different ($p < 0.05$) from A2 and A3. The protein content of A1 and A4 did not differ significantly ($p > 0.05$). The quantity and quality of protein plays a crucial role in diet. Proteins are essential constituents of all body tissues [26]. However, crude fibre was not detected in all the yoghurt samples and this correlates with the findings of the [27] which reported no fibre for all the various types of yoghurt produced from different sources.

Also, carbohydrate contents show significant difference ($p < 0.05$) across all the samples with A1 having the highest value followed by A3, A4 and A2. The low carbohydrate values in A2, A3, and A4 is attributed to the process of fermentation which converts carbohydrate basically lactose to lactic acid. This makes yoghurt an ideal food for lactose intolerant individuals [28].

Table 2 shows the peroxide value results of the yoghurt of samples. The result shows significant difference ($p < 0.05$) in the peroxide values of all the four samples. A1 had the least peroxide value, while A2 had the highest peroxide value. The peroxide value is a useful indication of the extent

of oxidation of lipid, fat and oil [29]. The peroxide value shows the degree of peroxidation and measure the amount of total peroxide in the substance. The onset of rancid taste begins when peroxide value is between 20 and 40 meq/ml.

Table 3 shows the free fatty acids result of the yoghurt samples. The result reveal that A2 has the highest percentage of free fatty acids, while A3 has the lowest percentage. The physiochemical quality of A2, A3, and A4 vary significantly ($p < 0.05$) in their percentage free fatty acid. A1 and A2 shows no significant difference ($p > 0.05$) in their percentage free fatty acids. The role of free fatty acids (FFAs) as a source of energy and their functions in energy transport within the body are well established. Equally, FFAs also play an important role in oxidative stress following cell membrane depolarization [30]. Free fatty acids are essential for the growth and development of vital organs, including the brain [31]. Clearly, fat is crucial for life, yet the body cannot synthesize certain kinds of fats. Rather, these fats are obtained from ingested food [31].

The result of the microbial count (coliform) is presented in Table 4. The result indicates zero coliforms in all the samples. This corresponds with the report by [19]. The Codex standards for fermented milk products require that yoghurt should contain no coliforms. The absence of coliform is a good indication of the Good Manufacturing Practices employed by the producers and handlers [19].

5.0 Conclusion

Yoghurt is a widely consumed dairy product in Birnin Kebbi Metropolis, Kebbi State, and its safety and quality are crucial for public health. This study assessed four different brands collected from various locations for selected safety and quality parameters. The results revealed all the four brands of yoghurts were of good physiochemical and microbial quality an indication of compliance with good manufacturing practice. Furthermore, these findings underscore the need for continual quality assessment and adherence to regulatory standards to ensure consistent product quality and safety in commercially sold yogurts in Kebbi state and by extension Nigeria.

6.0 Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, there is need for continual quality assessment and adherence to regulatory standards to ensure consistent product quality and safety in yogurts sold in Birnin Kebbi.

7.0 Acknowledgement

The authors wish to acknowledge the support of the Head of Department of Biochemistry and Molecular Biology, Federal University, Birnin Kebbi and other members for providing an enabling environment to successfully conduct this study.

8.0 Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest

9.0 References

- [1] Keta JN, Suberu HA, Aliero AA, Mohammed NK, Anas H, Mubarak A. Evaluation of Fungi Species from Commercial Yoghurts in Birnin Kebbi, Kebbi State Nigeria. *Equity Journal of Science and Technology*. 2019; 6: 72 -77
- [2] Ali AA, Bukar A. Comparative Evaluation on the Physicochemical, Proximate and Probiotic Status of Some Commercially Produced Yoghurt Stored Under Ambient Conditions. *International Journal of Engineering and Science*. 2020; 7:32-41.
- [3] Omola EM, Kawo AH, Shamsudeen U. Physicochemical, Sensory and Microbiological Qualities of Yoghurts brands solds in Kano metropolis, Bayero. *Journal of Pure and Applied Sciences*. 2014; 7: 26-30.
- [4] Santiago-Lopez L, Hernandez-Mendoza AH, Garcia HS, MatoHaro V, Vallejo-Cordoba B, Gonzales-Cordova AAF. The effects of consuming probiotic- fermented milk on the immune system: a review of scientific evidence. *International Journal of Dairy Technology*. 2015; 68: 153–165.
- [5] Ng EW, Yeung M, Tong, PS. Effects of yoghurt starter cultures on the survival of *Lactobacillus acidophilus*. *International Journal of Food Microbiology*, 2011; 169–175.
- [6] Tripathi MK, Giri SK. Probiotic functional foods: survival of probiotics during processing and storage. *Journal of Functional Foods*. 2014; 9: 225–241.
- [7] Abadia-Garcia L, Cardador A, Martindel ST. Influence of probiotic strains added to cottage cheese on generation of potentially antioxidant peptides, antilisterial activity, and survival of probiotic microorganisms in simulated gastrointestinal conditions. *International Dairy Journal*. 2013; 33: 191–197.
- [8] Kailasapathy K, Harmstorf I, Phillips M. Survival of *Lactobacillus acidophilus* and *Bifidobacterium animalis*ssp. *lactis* in stirred fruit yoghurts. *LWT-Food Science and Technology*. 2008; 41: 1317–1322.
- [9] Turgut T, Cakmakci S. Investigation of the possible use of probiotics in ice cream manufacture. *International Journal of Dairy Technology*, 2009; 62: 444–451.
- [10] Cakmakci S, Cetin B, Turgut T, Gurses M, Erdogan A. Probiotic properties, sensory qualities and storage stability of probiotic banana yogurts. *Turkish Journal of Veterinary and Animal Sciences*. 2012; 36: 231–2.
- [11] FAO/WHO. Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations and World Health Organization 2002.Guidelines for the Evaluation of Probiotics in Food. 2002.
- [12] Ammara H, Imran A. Nutritional evaluation of yoghurt prepared by different starter cultures and their physicochemical analysis during storage. *African Journal of Biotechnology*. 2010; 9: 2913-2917.
- [13] Ahmed I, Gulzar M, Shahzad F, Yaqub M, Zhoor T. Quality assessment of Yoghurt produced at large industrial and small scale. *Journal of Animal and Plant Science*. 2013; 6: 3-6.
- [14] Nigerian Meteorological Agency. *Climate Data for Kebbi State*. Retrieved July 18, 2024, retrieved from nimet.gov.ng 2020.
- [15] National Bureau of Statistics. *Kebbi State Statistical Handbook*. Retrieved July 18, 2024, from <https://www.nigerianstat.gov.ng/2021>.
- [16] AOAC. Association of Official Analytical Chemists. *Official Methods of Analysis of the Association of Analytical Chemists*. 18th ed. Washington, D. C. USA. 2012.
- [17] Gordon MA, Armenise E, White RP, Hirsch PR, Goulding KWT. A comparison of two colorimetric assays, based upon Lowry and Bradford techniques, to estimate total protein in soil extracts. *Soil Biology and Biochemistry*. 2013; 67:166-173.

- [18] Feng P, Weagant SD, Grant MA, Burkhardt W. Enumeration of *Escherichia coli* and the coliform bacteria. Chapter 4 in Bacteriological Analytical Manual. 8th ed. US Food and Drug Administration, Center for Food Safety and Applied Nutrition, College Park, MD. Accessed May 20, 2024.<http://www.fda.gov/Food/FoodScienceResearch/LaboratoryMethods/ucm064948.htm>2002.
- [19] Igbabul B, Shember J, Amove J. Physicochemical, microbiological and sensory evaluation of yoghurt sold in Makurdi metropolis. *African Journal of Food Science and Technology*. 2014; 5: 129-135.
- [20] Matela KS, Pillai MK., Ranthimo PM, Ntakatsane M. Analysis of Proximate Compositions and Physicochemical Properties of Some Yoghurt Samples from Maseru, Lesotho. *Journal of Food Science and Nutrition Research*; 2019; 2: 245-252.
- [21] Younus S, Masud T, Aziz T. Quality evaluation of market yoghurt in Dahi. *Pakistan Journal of Nutrition*. 2010; 1: 226-230.
- [22] EL Bakri JM, El Zubeir IEM. Chemical and microbiological evaluation of plain and Fruit yoghurt in Khartoum State, Sudan. *International Journal of Dairy Science*. 2009; 4: 1-7.
- [23] Oladipo IC, Atolagbe OO, Adetiba TM. Nutrition evaluation and microbiological analysis of yoghurt produced from full cream milk, tiger-nut milk, skimmed milk, and fresh cow milk. *Pensee Journal*. 2014; 76: 30-38.
- [24] Codex standard for fermentation was adopted in 2003. Codex Stan 243-2003 (Revised, 2010).<http://www.codexalimentarius.org/inp> ut/download/standards/.../CXS_243e.pdf Accessed on 12/7/2024.
- [25] Mbaeyi-Nwaoha IE, Umeh LC, Igbokwe CJ. Production and quality evaluation of flavouredyoghurt from graded levels of sweet variety of African bush mango “urigi” (*Irvingiagabonensis*) juiceand pulp. *Food Science and Technology*. 2017; 5: 56-69.
- [26] Sanni VR, Oladapo SS. Potential of carbon sequestration and storage by trees in and around B.A.M. University campus of Aurangabad city in Maharashtra, India. *International Journal of Scientific Development and Research*, 2018; 2: 28-33.
- [27] Food Standard Agency. Cance Mc Widowson. The composition of food, 6th edition. In: The nutritional composition of dairy products, the dairy council. <http://www.milk.co.uk/publications/default.aspx> 2002
- [28] Ehirim FN, Ndimantang, B.E. Production and evaluation of yoghurt from cow-soy milk blends. *Journal Agricultural and Food Science*. 2004; 3: 33–39.
- [29] Adgidzi EA, Abu JO. Effects of Processing Methods on The Quality of Yoghurt-Like Products from Tiger nut (*Cyperus esculentus*). *Production Agriculture and Technology*. 2014;10: 145-156
- [30] Zbigniew BK, Sumit S, Sonia S, Carmen G. Role of Free Fatty Acids in Physiological Conditions and Mitochondrial Dysfunction. *Food and Nutrition Sciences*.2013; 4: 6-15.
- [31] Wong SW, Kwon MJ, Choi AM, Kim HP, Nakahira K, Hwang DH. Fatty Acids Modulate TollLike Receptor 4 Activation Through Regulation of Receptor Dimerization and Recruitment into Lipid Rafts in a Reactive Oxygen Species-Dependent Manner. *Journal of Biological Chemistry*. 2009; 284: 27384-27392.

Copyright © 2024 by the authors. This article is an open access article under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>), which permits use, distribution and reproduction in other forums is permitted, provided the original author(s) and the copyright owner(s) are credited and that the original publication in this journal is cited, in accordance with accepted academic practice.